

Agroforestry in Germany

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Clarification of legal aspects in the field of agroforestry (e.g. coordination with landowners and integration of landscape elements).
- Existing demand for regional eco-compensation
- Policies and legal framework that affect agroforestry can have positive effects
- Unclear funding situation and bureaucratic hurdles
- Policies and legal framework that affect agroforestry can have negative effects
- Unclear responsibilities in the administration (Who is the contact person for agroforestry matters in the local administration?)

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	Germany		Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022
Nut level:	1		Silvopasture	2,17%	2,93%
Eurostat code:	DE3		Agrisilviculture	0,00%	0,00%
Area (km ²):	29.868		Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%
Population	2018	2022	Kitchen gardens	0,27%	0,09%
Population	6.117.535	6.215.340	Holding type	2016	2023
Density (p km ⁻²)	205	208	Natural person (ha)	1.460	1.300
Cover data	2018	2022	Legal person (ha)	280	290
Forest	28,78%	24,96%	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	100	330
Arable land	47,05%	23,10%	Natural person (holder)	40	30
Permanent crops	0,04%	0,00%	Legal person (holder)	10	10
Agroforestry	2,44%	3,01%	Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	10	5
Shrubland	0,58%	1,51%			
Grassland	12,95%	27,79%			

Regional Agricultural Area	Used	2016	2023
Farm number		50	50
Farm ha (UAA)		1.840	1.910
Animal populations (Thousand head)		2018	2023
Live bovine animals		-	1
Dairy cows		-	0
Non dairy cows		-	0
Live swine, domestic species		-	-
Live sheep		-	-
Live goats		-	-
CROPS (Hectares)		2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area		1.840	1.910
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)		640	590
Common wheat and spelt		40	-
Durum wheat		-	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)		390	300
Barley		60	90
Oats and spring cereal mixtures		70	60
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix		-	-
Rice		-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain		-	-
Industrial crops		50	-
Cotton seed and fibre		-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.		-	-
Fibre crops		-	-
Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants		-	-

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Plants harvested green from arable land	220	300
Green maize	-	-
Kitchen gardens	-	-

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	-
Forestry	-
Crop diversification including woody perennials	-
Crop rotation including woody perennials	-
Livestock including woody perennials	-
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	-
Woody perennials to add organic matter	-
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	-
Animal welfare using woody perennials	-
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	-
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	-
Interventions	-

References

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